

AIRBORNE LIDAR ESTIMATES OF PHOTOSYNTHESIS PROFILES

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ABSTRACT

The rate of photosynthesis in the ocean depends on the concentration of chlorophyll in the water, the light level, and the water temperature. The depth profile of chlorophyll concentration can be estimated by airborne backscatter lidar. Both the attenuation of a lidar pulse and the volume backscattering coefficient depend on chlorophyll concentration, and these dependences can be used in an iterative retrieval to estimate the chlorophyll profile. The chlorophyll concentration profile can also be used to estimate the attenuation of sunlight with depth, which can be used with a measurement of the incident sunlight at the aircraft to estimate the light level profile. The temperature profile is more difficult, but the sea-surface temperature can be measured from the aircraft and this temperature is constant through the mixed layer. The technique is illustrated using data from a lidar and visible and infrared radiometers on an aircraft over the Gulf of Mexico.

Index Terms— Lidar, oceanography, ocean optics, primary productivity

1. INTRODUCTION

Photosynthesis is the process by which carbon dioxide is converted to organic carbon. Understanding the rate at which this is occurring, known as primary productivity, is critical to modeling the effects of anthropogenic CO₂ emissions on climate. About half of global primary productivity occurs in the ocean [1, 2], and accurate monitoring of this process requires the use of remote sensing techniques.

There has been a significant effort on estimating global primary production of the ocean using passive remote sensing [3-5]. Ocean color measurements from satellite are used to estimate surface chlorophyll concentration, which is assumed to be constant at depths where there is sufficient light for photosynthesis to occur. These estimates do not always agree with *in situ* measurements, and vertical inhomogeneity in the distribution of chlorophyll has been suggested as a possible reason for the discrepancies [5].

This paper considers estimation of productivity profiles using airborne lidar. Section 2 describes a model of photosynthesis that uses profiles of chlorophyll concentration, light level, and temperature. Section 3 describes the biooptical model of the signal from an elastic lidar that is used to retrieve chlorophyll concentration profiles from the lidar return. Section 4 provides examples

of photosynthesis profiles, and Section 5 provides discussion and conclusions.

2. PHOTOSYNTHESIS MODEL

The vertical profile of the rate of production of organic carbon by photosynthesis can be estimated using the following model [3, 4]:

$$P = P_{opt}^B D \frac{\left\{ 1 - \exp\left[-\frac{E(z)}{E_{max}}\right] \right\} \exp[-\beta_p E(z)]}{\left\{ 1 - \exp\left[-\frac{E_{opt}}{E_{max}}\right] \right\} \exp[-\beta_p E_{opt}]} chl(z), \quad (1)$$

where P is the daily primary production of organic carbon ($\text{mg m}^{-3} \text{ day}^{-1}$), P_{opt}^B is the maximum carbon fixation rate within the water column, ($\text{mg C (mg chl)}^{-1} \text{ hour}^{-1}$), D is the photoperiod (hour), E is the photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) (mol quanta m^{-2}), E_{max} is the daily PAR at the inflection point between light limitation and light saturation in the absence of photoinhibition, β_p is a photoinhibition parameter, E_{opt} is the daily PAR at the depth of PC_{max} , and chl is the chlorophyll concentration (mg m^{-3}).

$$P_{opt}^B = 1.2956 + 0.2749T + 0.0617T^2 - 0.0205T^3 + 2.462 \times 10^{-3}T^4 - 1.348 \times 10^{-4}T^5 + 3.4132 \times 10^{-6}T^6 - 3.27 \times 10^{-8}T^7, \quad (2)$$

where T is temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$).

$$E_{max} = 0.3195E_0, \quad (3)$$

where E_0 is the daily PAR at the surface in mol m^{-2} .

$$E_{opt} = E_0 \exp\left(0.00137 - 0.075E_0 + 0.00171E_0^2 - 1.84 \times 10^{-5}E_0^3 + 7.56 \times 10^{-8}E_0^4\right). \quad (4)$$

$$\beta_p = 0.1 \quad \text{for } E_0 \leq 3 \text{ mol m}^{-2} \\ = -0.0203 \ln(E_0) + 0.124 \quad \text{for } E_0 > 3 \text{ mol m}^{-2} \quad (5)$$

To illustrate the model, the rate of production of carbon, normalized by the concentration of chlorophyll, was computed for uniform concentrations of chlorophyll of 0.1, 1, and 10 mg m^{-3} and a constant temperature of 10 $^{\circ}$ C (Fig. 1). Daily PAR at the surface was calculated using MODTRAN5 for year day 180, clear skies, and the default mid-latitude summer atmosphere. For all three cases, the model predicts that productivity peaks at about three times the surface value at a depth that depends on chl . The depth of the peak productivity is well within the depth range that can typically be measured by airborne lidar [6].

Figure 1. Plot of productivity profile, P , normalized by chlorophyll concentration, chl , for a clear summer day at 45° N latitude. Curves are labeled by the value of chl , which is assumed to be constant with depth, z . $T = 10^\circ$ C for all cases.

3. LIDAR PROFILES OF CHLOROPHYLL

Airborne lidar can provide profiles of optical backscattering along the path of the aircraft to depths of about three times the diffuse attenuation length, or as deep as 50 m for a lidar operating at 532 nm in clear water [6]. This technique has been used to document the widespread occurrence of thin (< 3-5 m) plankton layers in the ocean [7, 8]. These layers, as in the example of Fig. 2, often occur at the pycnocline [9, 10], and have been used to directly measure internal-wave displacements [11, 12].

Figure 2. Relative lidar backscatter (darker gray is more backscatter) as a function of depth, z , and distance along the flight track, d .

To convert lidar backscatter profiles into chl profiles requires the use of an appropriate bio-optical model. To do this, we will assume a wide-beam lidar operating at a wavelength of 532 nm and Case 1 waters, in which the optical properties are primarily determined by phytoplankton. Under these conditions, the attenuation of the lidar is given by the diffuse attenuation coefficient [13, 14], which can be approximated by [15, 16]

$$K_d = 0.0452 + 0.0474 chl^{0.67}. \quad (6)$$

The lidar backscatter, which is the volume backscatter coefficient for a scattering angle of π , is given by [15-17]

$$\beta = 1.94 \times 10^{-4} + 6.28 \times 10^{-5} [7 - \log_{10}(chl)] chl^{0.766}. \quad (7)$$

The lidar signal depends on both β and K_d according to [6, 18]

$$S = A\beta \exp\left(-2 \int_0^z K_d dz'\right), \quad (8)$$

where A is a calibration constant that depends on the parameters of the lidar. As long as the water properties are accurately described by Eqs. (6) and (7), this relationship can be inverted to estimate profiles of chl [8]. The inversion begins at the surface ($z = 0$), and $chl(0)$ is estimated from $S(0)$ by solving Eq.(7). $K_d(0)$ is estimated from $chl(0)$ using Eq. (6), and this value is used to calculate the attenuation between $z = 0$ and the next lidar sample at $z = 0.11$ m. This attenuation is used with $S(0.11)$ to estimate $chl(0.11)$. This process continues in depth increments of 0.11 m until the profile is complete. Figure 3 presents an example of the result of such an inversion.

Figure 3. Retrieved chlorophyll concentration, chl , as a function of depth, z , for a single lidar profile in the Gulf of Mexico.

4. PROFILES OF PRODUCTIVITY

With an estimate of the chlorophyll profiles, we can estimate the profile of PAR using [19]

$$K_{PAR} = 0.121chl^{0.428}. \quad (9)$$

For relatively low-flying aircraft, the PAR at the surface can be approximated by the value at the aircraft, which can be measured with a radiometer.

Temperature profiles are more difficult to measure from an aircraft. It is possible to measure temperature profiles using either Brillouin [20, 21] or Raman [22, 23] lidar, but neither technique has been widely applied. Sea surface temperature can easily be measured from an aircraft using a thermal radiometer, and this temperature can be used through the mixed layer of the upper ocean.

Figure 4 presents the profile of productivity calculated from the chlorophyll profile of Figure 3, the incident irradiance measured at the aircraft altitude of 300 m, and the temperature measured with a thermal radiometer on the aircraft. For this case, temperature was assumed to be constant to the depth where significant chlorophyll concentrations were measured.

Figure 4. Estimated profile of primary productivity, P , as a function of depth, z , for the lidar profile of Fig. 3.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The example provided demonstrates that it is possible to estimate the profile of primary productivity in the ocean using a calibrated backscatter lidar, an upward-looking visible radiometer, and a downward-looking thermal radiometer. The depth profile of chlorophyll concentration provided by the lidar is important, because photosynthesis is most efficient at a depth near K_{PAR}^{-1} . In the example presented, this means that the higher chlorophyll

concentration at the surface is less effective than the layer of enhanced chlorophyll at 10-12 m.

One problem with this technique is that the inversion is sensitive to errors in calibration. For the example, the calibration constant was inferred from the data. This was done by selecting a region where the signal was decaying exponentially and assuming constant attenuation and backscatter over this region. In the future, a better calibration is needed, either in the laboratory or in the field. One possibility that is being considered is to use ocean color information to constrain a simultaneous retrieval of calibration coefficient and chl profile.

Improvements in the bio-optical model are also needed. The model used here was primarily developed for passive remote sensing applications. Comparisons between lidar measurements and *in situ* data have been made, but more are necessary to refine the relationships. Improvements for active remote sensing would include relationships for lidar ratio [16] and depolarization [18].

Despite these limitations, this work suggests that measurements of primary productivity are possible from aircraft. This raises the possibility of synoptic measurements over large scales.

6. REFERENCES

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